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PHARMACOGNOSY OF *CHATURBEEJA*

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Abstract

Global demand of herbal medicine is increased day by day. To compensate this demand, need more raw material, but due to less cultivation of medicinal plants it is difficult to provide needed herbs for production. Because of which the adulteration and substitution is increasing day by day. So, it is become difficult to make sure that the drug which is available in market is original or adulterated. To confirm the originality of drug there are many analysis methods are available. Pharmacognosy is one of them by which one can confirm the identity of plant and to check the impurities or adulteration in the herbal formulation. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Chaturbeeja* was carried out. *Chaturbeeja* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Methika* (*Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn.), *Chandrashura* (*Lapidium sativum* Linn.), *Kalajaji* (*Nigella sativa* Linn.), *Yavanika* (*Trachyspermum ammi* Linn.). Slides of each ingredient of *Chaturbeeja* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Chaturbeeja* shows fibers, fragments of tissues, trichomes, crystals etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Chaturbeeja* helps in the correct identification of *Methika* (*Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn.), *Chandrashura* (*Lapidium sativum* Linn.), *Kalajaji* (*Nigella sativa* Linn.) and *Yavanika* (*Trachyspermum ammi* Linn.). Powder microscopy is one of the simplest methods for correct identification of herbal drug in polyherbal formulation. This helps in standardization of new drug and polyherbal formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

The ancient Indian medical system which is known as a Ayurveda is a profound science that not only emphasizes on treating diseases but also give importance to remain healthy. In Ayurveda there is a description about *Bheshaja Chatushpada- Bhishak*(Physician), *Bheshaja*(Drug), *Paricharaka*(Attendant) and *Rogi*(Patient) is available without these four any treatment cannot success. In these *Bheshaja* which means *Dravya* – Drug which is used for treatment. Global demand of herbal medicine is increased day by day. To compensate this demand, need more raw material, but due to less cultivation of medicinal plants it is difficult to provide needed herbs for production. Because of which the adulteration and substitution is increasing day by day. So, it is become difficult to make sure that the drug which is available in market is original or adulterated.

To confirm the originality of drug there are many analysis methods are available. Pharmacognosy is one of them by which one can confirm the identity of plant and to check the impurities or adulteration in the herbal formulation. Here, for the present study *Chaturbeeja* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Chaturbeeja* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved.¹ It contains *Methika* (*Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn. Family - Fabaceae), *Chandrashura* (*Lapidium sativum* Linn. Family- Brassicaceae), *Kalajaji* (*Nigella sativa* Linn. Family- Ranunculaceae), *Yavanika* (*Trachyspermum ammi* Linn. Family- Apiaceae).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Chaturbeeja*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, trichomes etc. in the powder of *Methika* (*Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn.), *Chandrashura* (*Lapidium sativum* Linn.), *Kalajaji* (*Nigella sativa* Linn.), *Yavanika* (*Trachyspermum ammi* Linn.)
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Chaturbeeja was used for the powder microscopy. *Chaturbeeja* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Methika* (*Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn.), *Chandrashura* (*Lapidium sativum* Linn.), *Kalajaji* (*Nigella sativa* Linn.), *Yavanika* (*Trachyspermum ammi* Linn.). *Beeja* of these four drugs were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Chaturbeeja* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁵

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. Powder microscopic characters found in *Methika*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Methika</i>	Figure no.
1.	Epidermis of the testa	Fig. 1a
2.	Fibres	Fig. 1b
3.	Outermost layer of endosperm	Fig. 1c

4.	Epidermis	Fig. 1d
5.	Part of cotyledon in section view	Fig. 1e

Table No. Powder microscopic characters found in Chandrashura

No.	Characteristics of Chandrashura	Figure no.
1.	Fragments of cotyledon in surface view filled with aleurone grains	Fig. 2a
2.	Fibres	Fig. 2b, 2c
3.	Epidermis of testa in surface view embaded with mucilage	Fig. 2d

Table No. Powder microscopic characters found in Kalajaji

No.	Characteristics of Kalajaji	Figure no.
1.	Oilglobules	Fig. 3a
2.	Fibres	Fig. 3b
3.	Fragments showing thick-walled cells of seed coat	Fig. 3c
4.	Thick-walled cells of seed coat with oil globules and fibres	Fig. 3d

Table No. Powder microscopic characters found in Yavanika

No.	Characteristics of Yavanika	Figure no.
1.	Fiber	Fig. 4a
2.	Unicellular warty trichomes	Fig. 4b
3.	Endosperm	Fig. 4c
4.	Striated cuticle in surface view	Fig. 4d

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Chaturbeeja* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Chaturbeeja* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Methika* shows, Epidermis of the Testa, Fibers, Outermost layer of endosperm, Epidermis, Part of cotyledon in section view. Powder microscopy of *Chandrashura* shows Fragments of cotyledon in surface view filled with aleurone grains, Fibers, Epidermis of Testa in surface view embedded with mucilage. Powder microscopy of *Kalajaji* shows, Oil globules, Fibers, Fragments showing thick-walled cells of seed coat, Thick-walled cells of seed coat with oil globules and fibers. Powder microscopy of *Yavanika* shows, Fiber, Unicellular warty trichomes, Endosperm, Striated cuticle in surface view.

Standardization of compound formulations of Ayurved is quite difficult and complicated. But it is essential for assuring the quality and safety of herbal drugs thus making herbal drugs viable for the use. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Chaturbeeja* was carried out and their

microscopic characters were noted. These characters might help in detecting impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

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Powder microscopic characters found in Methika

Epidermis of the testa

Fig. 1a

Fragment of fibre

Fig. 1b

Outer most layer of the endosperm in surface view

Fig. 1c

Epidermis

Fig. 1d

Part of the cotyledon in sectional view

Fig. 1e

Powder microscopic characters found in Chandrashura

Fragments of cotyledon in surface view filled with aleurone grains

Fig. 2a

Fibre

Fig. 2b

Fibre

Fig. 2c

Phc

Fibre

Epidermis of testa in surface view embaded with mucilage

Fig. 2d

Powder microscopic characters found in Kalajji

Oilglobules

Fig. 3a

Fibre

Fig. 3b

Fragments showing thick-walled cells of seed coat

Fig. 3c

Thick-walled cells of seed coat with oil globules and fibres

Fig. 3d

Powder microscopic characters found in Yavanika

Fibre

Fig. 3a

Unicellular warty trichome

Fig. 3b

Endosperm

Fig. 3c

Fig. 3d

CONCLUSION:

The current study's findingsaid in the identification of herbal formulation like *Chaturbeeja*. As per this study an Ayurvedic formulation Chaturbeeja have structures like epidermal cells, oil globules, fibres, cotyledon fragments, trichomes etc.

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